

ON THE PROBLEM OF OPTIMIZING THE INTRODUCTION OF TERMS IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract The article discusses the issue of optimizing the process of learning a foreign language at a higher education institution, reveals the goals and objectives of teaching a foreign language at a higher education institution. The essence of the classroom and extracurricular foreign language activity of students in a non-linguistic university is revealed in detail, namely: tasks, purpose, specificity, requirements, forms of conduct.

Keywords: Learning optimization, classroom and extracurricular foreign language activities of student.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается вопрос оптимизации процесса изучения иностранного языка в высшем учебном заведении, раскрываются цели и задачи преподавания иностранного языка в высшем учебном заведении. Подробно раскрывается сущность аудиторной и внеаудиторной иноязычной деятельности студентов в неязыковом вузе, а именно: задачи, цель, специфика, требования, формы поведения.

Ключевые слова: оптимизация обучения, аудиторная и внеаудиторная иноязычная деятельность студента.

At present, international contacts in industry, culture, and economics impose on modern specialists a high demand for communication in foreign languages. One of these languages is English. Basic knowledge of a foreign language, which students receive even in secondary schools, form the initial communicative competence. However, the implementation of learning tasks is faced with a number of difficulties, such as a lack of positive attitude of students towards the foreign language being studied and the lack of a language environment. In higher education institutions, students have already chosen a profession and begin their activities in accordance with the requirements that apply to the specialists of their chosen profession. This is professionalism, culture and ability to work with imported equipment, properly understand the various instructions and documentation in English, communicate in various production situations, etc. The main goal of vocational education is to train a qualified worker of an appropriate level and profile, competitive in the labor market, competent, fluent in his profession and oriented in related fields of activity, ready for continuous professional growth, social and professional mobility. The ways to optimize the educational process at the university include: -The choice of teaching methods, based on the characteristics of the individual students. -Optimization of the means of teaching a foreign language in the system of practical language training (textbook, technical means of training, curriculum). The main function of teaching aids is to optimize the educational process, to introduce, as far as possible, to the language environment, as well as to the future professional activities of students. -Improvement of foreign language teaching methods (organization of students'

independent work, extracurricular work). -Creating a psychological microclimate in the educational environment as one of the conditions of the learning process. -The use of student-centered approach in the learning process. -Purposeful work with texts. Let us dwell in detail on the use of a personality-oriented approach in the process of learning foreign languages and working with texts.

The student-centered approach gradually enters the practice of teaching foreign languages. It attracts the teacher with the opportunity for a creative approach to learning, the use of interactive problem and project assignments. It is interesting for the student as well. he gets the opportunity to use his own training materials and topics for discussion, to take responsibility for the form of assimilation and for the final result, i.e. what he should learn for an occupation or a series of occupations, where and how he can apply new knowledge and skills in life, using the foreign language being studied.

The concept of problematics can serve as a fundamental component of a personality-oriented approach (J. Dewey). Problem learning creates the condition for the creative mastery of a foreign language, i.e. It contributes to the development of students' intellectual abilities. Problem is realized through the creation of problem situations. The peculiarity of the problem situation in a foreign language is that it includes a speech component, a replica of the interlocutor as a speech stimulus. So, a statement will be a reaction to expressed doubt, to a question, a message of information or its silence. The conditions of interaction between the speech situation partners are set by the problem itself: where the first partner is characterized by ignorance, the second must have this knowledge; where at one right, at another - duties, etc. Thus, in the formulation of an educational problem speech situation, it is necessary to reflect the main parameters: set the condition of the situation, put forward the problem question, create a motivating speech stimulus that encourages the resolution of the problem situation. Occupation is the main organizational element of the learning process, which is used to solve specific practical, educational, educational and developmental tasks that ensure the achievement of final goals. When teaching students, it is important to bring up the tasks of the lesson, since they must be accepted by them. Students need to see, understand what they have learned in class, evaluate activities, psychologically and in fact, prepare for independent work outside the classroom. The main psychological factor determining a positive approach to learning a foreign language is a high degree of motivation and interest in a foreign language as a means of speech communication within the chosen specialty. When developing a cycle of classes on a particular topic, a careful selection of language material is carried out, from the point of view of communicative significance, lexical and grammatical variability, and oral usage.

At the same time, the form of exercises and the formulation of tasks should reflect the characteristic features of professional oral communication within the specialty under study. Therefore, when compiling assignments for them, such requirements as motivation, communicative orientation, situational conditionality and structural formation are presented. According to its content, the exercises create a speech situation in the class. They are built on textual material and speech patterns used in a wide variety of communication situations. Also, the goal of a significant part of the exercises is the formation of dialogic speech and monologue speech. To do this, colloquial formulas (speech etiquette), structural elements of dialogical communication, speech patterns characteristic of the spoken style of the language, such as questionanswer exercises, frontal conversation on a topic (text, picture), exercises in a

given situation, are systematically tested with students. the game of translator, the conference, or round table.

Thus, when training students of the third year of technical specialties in foreign language classes in a non-linguistic university, it is necessary to take into account many factors that lead to the solution of the goals and objectives. Not a small role in the process of optimizing learning is work with texts. They should feel that the material offered to them will be necessary for communication in various areas of their future profession, social motivation. For students, the most interesting and stimulating their educational activities will be texts with a professional theme that have cognitive value, containing problematic situations that lead to thinking, cognitive motivation. Training materials create an environment for future professional activities. Repeated repetition of the same or varying production situations contributes to a sufficiently solid assimilation of all the entered educational information. The Russian equivalents of the foreign terms introduced to students correspond to the terminology they encounter in the classroom for special subjects. The training material is selected by careful selection of language units that will be useful to the student in their practical activities. Vocabulary, cliché phrases prepare students for professional and intercultural communication: greetings, polite addresses, requests, questions, suggestions, farewell phrases, etc. Subject texts introduce the learner into the setting of his future profession. Students study, activate and fix specialized vocabulary and terminology in various situations, grammatical structures, learn to make dialogues and monologues according to a certain algorithm.

Out-of-class foreign language activity is an integral part of the basic course and contributes to a deeper study of language material, increases motivation to the subject, considering the personal and age characteristics of students, contributes to the implementation of the main goals of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university, contributes to the formation of foreign language competence in general. Thus, as a result of the intensification of educational activities, a foreign language acquires a personal meaning for students, becomes a constantly active factor in the motivation of learning. Professionally-oriented learning is one of the means to improve the effectiveness of teaching English.

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